

High yield low temperature biocompatible activation of biochar for sustainable supercapacitors

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a sustainable and efficient method for producing activated carbon from biomass-derived biochar for use in electrochemical supercapacitors. Biochar sourced from wood chips supplied by Carbofex Ltd., a European Biochar Certificate (EBC) certified biomass producer renowned for carbon-negative biochar, was hydrothermally activated using potassium bicarbonate (KHCO₃) at 200 °C for 36 h. This simplified activation method achieved a yield of approximately 90 %, in contrast to the 30–70 % typically obtained with conventional activation methods such as KOH or CO₂, where extensive carbon burn-off is common. Beyond yield, the process enhanced the BET-specific surface area from ~420 to ~1006 m²/g and improved thermal stability by removing volatile fractions, generating a microporous network with structural robustness and ion-accessible porosity. Electrochemical characterization showed that the activated carbon achieved a specific capacitance of 27.13 F/g at 0.08 A/g, which is comparable to commercially available activated carbon YP80-F (30 F/g) and retained 85 % of its capacitance after 10,000 cycles. The activated carbon device performed on par with commercial materials, indicating its promise for practical supercapacitor use. This mild, non-corrosive activation process using sustainable precursors offers a scalable alternative to conventional methods, avoiding the environmental and safety risks associated with agents like KOH.

1. Introduction

Carbon plays a central role in both natural systems and industrial processes, from forming the backbone of biological molecules to influencing global climate policy. Converting lignocellulosic waste into valuable carbon materials supports a circular bioeconomy by improving resource efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas emissions [1–3]. Among carbonaceous materials, activated carbons (ACs) occupy a privileged position because they combine chemical inertness, thermal stability, readily tunable surface chemistry and exceptionally high internal surface areas that frequently exceed 1000 m²/g [4]. These properties have long supported applications in adsorption and catalysis and now drive renewed interest in energy storage, where double-layer capacitance benefits from large, accessible surface areas and well-organized porosity [5–12]. Recent developments further emphasize how finely tuned pore hierarchies and surface chemistry directly influence ion transport and electrolyte wetting in sustainable carbon

electrodes [13]. Designing ACs that deliver large, fast wetting surface areas without compromising sustainability has therefore become a pressing research topic.

Biochar is an especially attractive precursor because of its negative carbon footprint and compliance with sustainability standards. The material used in this study was supplied by Carbofex Ltd. in Finland, one of the first companies worldwide to receive the European Biochar Certificate (EBC). Their wood-chip biochar has a moderate surface area of about 420 m²/g, low ash content, and minimal contamination, which makes it both environmentally compatible and safe to handle. Conventional activation routes rely on either physical activation i.e., gasifying char with steam or CO₂ above 800 °C, or chemical activation with strong dehydrating or oxidising agents such as KOH, NaOH, ZnCl₂ or H₃PO₄ [14–16]. Physical activation is energy intensive and often yields broad pore size distributions, whereas chemical activation can generate ultrahigh surface areas (>2000 m²/g) and well-developed micro and mesoporosity but at the cost of handling highly corrosive reagents and

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producing salt rich effluents [14–17]. KOH, the benchmark chemical activator, is categorised as “extreme danger”; its corrosivity and large water neutralisation demand severely limit scaleup beyond laboratory batches [18]. Consequently, most commercial ACs for electrochemical applications (e.g., Kuraray’s coconut shell derived YP-80F) are still manufactured by steam activation, accepting lower pore development to meet environmental regulations [18].

In response, recent research has shifted toward greener activation chemistries. Alkali carbonates and bicarbonates (K_2CO_3 , $KHCO_3$, Na_2CO_3) have emerged as less hazardous alternatives that reproduce much of the textural development obtained with KOH while markedly reducing causticity, wastewater processing, and equipment corrosion [19–22]. These advances align with broader efforts toward eco-designed electrode materials, where both energy performance and material safety are equally prioritized [23]. During heat treatment, bicarbonate decomposes to CO_2 and K_2CO_3 , which reacts mildly with the carbon matrix, etching pore walls and intercalating potassium vapour between graphene layers without the violent solid liquid reactions characteristic of KOH. These milder conditions not only preserve precursor morphology yielding higher packing densities, a desirable property for volumetric energy storage but also increase carbon yield by avoiding excessive burn off.

In parallel with advances in activation chemistry, hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC) has reemerged as a low energy, CO_2 negative route for converting wet biomass into carbonaceous solids. HTC occurs between 150 and 350 °C under the self-generated pressure of subcritical water and is valued for its simplicity, feedstock flexibility, and environmental compatibility [24]. However, pristine hydrochars are usually amorphous spheres with modest surface area ($<150\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) and therefore require post-activation or templating to become electrochemically relevant [25]. Recent studies also show that even modest adjustments to hydrochar surface chemistry can greatly influence capacitance, underscoring the importance of controlled activation environments [26]. Integrating activation chemistries directly into the hydrothermal step so called hydrothermal activation, offers an elegant path to porous carbons with minimal energy input and processing steps.

Catalytic graphitisation, traditionally performed above 2500 °C, can be achieved at $\leq 1000\text{ °C}$ when transition metals (Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, etc.) are present [27]. When such catalysts are introduced during HTC, they serve simultaneously as in-situ templates and graphitisation promoters, giving rise to diverse morphologies hollow spheres, nanoflakes, even two-dimensional graphitic sheets at a fraction of the energy cost of traditional high temperature treatments. Such structural evolution is crucial, as ion accessibility and interfacial transport strongly depend on pore continuity and wettability in aqueous systems [28]. Yet few studies have explored thorough activation under hydrothermal conditions, and based on authors best knowledge no one has combined it with sustainable activation agents [29,30].

Against this backdrop, we report a one-pot, low-temperature strategy for converting commercial wood chip biochar into high-performance porous carbon using potassium bicarbonate ($KHCO_3$) as both an activator and an internal pore-forming agent. Biochar, a carbon-negative material produced via slow pyrolysis in oxygen-limited conditions sourced from Carbofex Ltd. [31], offers a sustainable and renewable feedstock with a respectable surface area ($\sim 420\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). However, this is still insufficient for advanced electrochemical applications. In our method, the biochar is milled to $<100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, mixed with aqueous $KHCO_3$, and subjected to hydrothermal treatment at just 200 °C for 36 h. Under these mild conditions, in-situ CO_2 evolution and potassium intercalation drive pore development, increasing the BET surface area to $\sim 1000\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ while maintaining a high carbon yield exceeding 90 %. This gentle approach avoids the harsh chemicals, corrosive waste, and energy-intensive steps associated with traditional activation processes such as KOH or acid treatment.

Our study is at the intersection of three converging trends: (i) greener chemical activation without highly corrosive agents; (ii) low

temperature hydrothermal routes capable of handling activation; and (iii) the urgent need for high surface area carbons to power next generation supercapacitors and related electrochemical technologies. By demonstrating that $KHCO_3$ can deliver commercial grade porosity under hydrothermal conditions, we provide a scalable, environment friendly pathway for producing activated carbons that rival or surpass traditional KOH activated materials. Ultimately, integrating carbonate based activation with HTC expands the toolkit for sustainable carbon material synthesis and supports the broader transition toward low carbon energy storage solutions.

2. Experimental method

2.1. Materials

Spruce derived biochar, used as the AC precursor, was sourced from Carbofex [31], a company known for high quality biochar derived from wood chips. Potassium bicarbonate ($KHCO_3$) and Hydrochloric acid (HCl) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2. Preparation of biochar for activation

To prepare biochar for activation, raw biochar (sourced in 5 cm chunks) was initially reduced to finer particles to facilitate uniform activation and maximize surface area (see Fig. 1). The biochar was first pre-ground using a mortar and pestle, ensuring initial particle size reduction. Following this the pre-ground biochar was sieved through a 100- μm mesh to remove oversized particles and achieve a consistent feed size for subsequent milling. The sieved biochar was then subjected to ball milling in a Retsch PM 100 planetary ball mill with the following setting, a speed of 400 rpm, a 200 ml sample chamber, and 10 mm diameter grinding balls. The batch composition consisted of 80 balls and 80 ml of powder per milling round, maintaining a consistent powder to ball ratio to optimize grinding efficiency. After milling, the biochar was sieved through a 50- μm mesh to achieve the desired particle size distribution. This precise particle size reduction process was essential to ensure uniform gas penetration during activation and enhance the surface area and pore structure in the final activated carbon product.

2.3. Chemical and physical activation

The biochar activation process employed a combined chemical and physical activation (see Fig. 1). Initially, biochar was chemically activated by mixing it with a $KHCO_3$ solution in different weight ratios. The mixture was stirred ensuring an even distribution of the activating agent. The dried $KHCO_3$ impregnated biochar was then transferred to Teflon line hydrothermal reactor for activation. The drying oven, VWR® VENTI-Line® Prime, temperature was raised to 200 °C, as this is the decomposition temperature of $KHCO_3$ [32]. The biochar was maintained at this temperature for 24 and 36 h to allow sufficient interaction between the biochar and $KHCO_3$, optimizing pore development and surface area. According to different parameters activated carbons are represented by HAC_xYY , here, “x” represents the $KHCO_3$ concentration and “YY” the activation duration in hours. After activation, the carbon was allowed to cool naturally within the furnace. The cooled material was then subjected to washing with 0.1 M HCl to remove residual salts and inorganic impurities, followed by multiple rinses with deionized water, ethanol and acetone until the pH was neutral. The washing process was conducted using a vacuum filtration unit to ensure thorough rinsing. Finally, the washed activated carbon was dried at 120 °C overnight to remove residual moisture, yielding a material ready for electrochemical characterization.

2.4. Fabrication of electrodes

The activated carbon (3.09 g) was dispersed in deionized water (2 g)

and a 50X objective lens. A diode-pumped solid-state laser with a wavelength of 532 nm and an output power of 30 mW was employed as the excitation source. Spectra were collected over the range of 500–3200 c/m, with each spectrum obtained as the average of 10 acquisitions, each with an integration time of 40 s.

2.7. Electrochemical characterization

Electrochemical characterization of the supercapacitors was carried out using a Maccor 4300 electrochemical workstation (Maccor Inc., USA) for galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) and cyclic voltammetry (CV), and a Zahner Zennium electrochemical workstation (Zahner-Elektrik GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) for electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). CV and GCD measurements were conducted across various scan rates and current densities to evaluate the capacitive behavior, specific capacitance, and rate capability. The SCs underwent three charge-discharge cycles between 0 and 1.2 V, followed by a 30 min voltage hold at 1.2 V for stabilization. Capacitance was determined from the GCD discharge curve using a constant current between 0.96 and 0.48 V. Leakage current was assessed by holding the device at 1.2 V for 1 h, and ESR was calculated from the IR drop during discharge at 10 mA. This method is in accordance with international industrial standard IEC 62391-1. This entire procedure was repeated at current levels of 1, 3, and 10 mA. Specific capacitance and ESR values were calculated from GCD data using standard electrochemical equations [34].

$$ESR = \frac{V_{drop}}{\Delta I} \quad (1)$$

$$C = \frac{(I \times \Delta t)}{m \times \Delta V} \quad (2)$$

In these formulas, V_{drop} is defined as the voltage drop, and ΔI as the change in current associated with internal resistance. The variable I denotes the applied current, while Δt refers to the duration of device discharge during the galvanostatic charge-discharge process. Additionally, specific energy (E , Wh/kg) and specific power (P , W/kg) of the devices were calculated using the following equations [42–45].

$$E = \frac{C \times V^2}{3.6 \times 2} \quad (3)$$

$$P = \frac{3600 \times E}{\Delta t} \quad (4)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Material characterization

The XRD patterns of the biochar and hydrothermally activated

carbon HAC_{236} , shown in Fig. 2(a), reveal clear structural changes induced by $KHCO_3$ activation. Both samples exhibit broad diffraction peaks characteristic of amorphous-like or turbostratic carbon structures. In particular, the broad (002) peak around $24^\circ 2\theta$ is associated with disordered graphitic layer stacking, while the weak (100) peak near $44^\circ 2\theta$ corresponds to limited in-plane aromatic ordering [46–48]. The broadness and low intensity of these peaks indicate small graphitic domains and a high degree of structural disorder, which is typical for activated carbons.

In addition, HAC_{236} displays an extra diffraction feature in the range of approximately $29\text{--}30^\circ 2\theta$ that is absent in the pristine biochar. This feature is attributed to potassium-containing species, such as potassium carbonate K_2CO_3 , formed during the activation process. Standard XRD patterns of K_2CO_3 show prominent peaks in this region [49]. This interpretation is further corroborated by XPS analysis, which shows an approximately fourfold increase in carbonate species after activation, increasing from 1.05 % in the biochar to 4.15 % in HAC_{236} . The combined XRD and XPS results therefore provide consistent chemical and structural evidence for the formation of K_2CO_3 during $KHCO_3$ activation, in line with the proposed activation mechanism [55].

Raman spectra of the HAC_{236} (Fig. 2(b)) and biochar (Fig. 2(c)) further corroborate the XRD observations and confirm the disordered nature of the carbon framework. Both samples exhibit broad and partially overlapping D and G bands typical of amorphous-like sp^2 carbon. The ID/IG ratio increases from 0.80 in the biochar to 1.00 in HAC_{236} , indicating an increase in defect density and a reduction in the average graphitic domain size after activation [50]. This increase in disorder is consistent with the reduced structural ordering inferred from the broad and weak XRD peaks and reflects pore formation and basal plane edge opening rather than enhanced graphitisation.

The defect level of HAC_{236} is comparable to values reported for established activated carbons, including commercial YP80F and recently published activated carbon materials [51]. Taken together, the XRD, Raman, and XPS results provide mutually consistent evidence of activation-induced disorder, carbonate formation, and pore development, which support the improved electrochemical performance of HAC_{236} .

The thermal stability of biochar and activated carbons was evaluated through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), with the weight loss profiles shown in Fig. 3(a). TGA was conducted under a 40:60 nitrogen-to-air gas mixture, for evaluating the oxidative stability of carbon materials, as pure air can cause rapid or complete combustion. The TGA curves reveal three main degradation stages. The first stage ($150^\circ C$) corresponds to the evaporation of physically adsorbed moisture, with biochar showing higher mass loss than AC due to its greater hydrophilicity. The second stage ($200\text{--}500^\circ C$) reflects the decomposition of volatile organic compounds. Biochar undergoes rapid weight loss, indicating a higher fraction of unstable material, while activated carbons exhibit a more

Fig. 2. (a) XRD spectra of Biochar and HAC_{236} , Raman spectra of (b) HAC_{236} and (c) biochar.

Fig. 3. (a) Thermogravimetric analysis of biochar and hydrothermally activated carbons and (b) the adsorption and desorption curves of N_2 at 77 K for HAC_{236} (the inset displays the pore size distribution).

controlled degradation. HAC_{236} demonstrates a stable weight retention profile in this range, suggesting effective removal of volatiles during activation, leading to a structurally robust carbon matrix. The final stage (500–800 °C) represents the degradation of the carbon framework. Biochar shows significant decomposition, leaving a higher residual mass, whereas activated carbons have lower final weight loss, confirming improved thermal resistance. Although HAC_{136} retains more mass, its earlier onset of degradation suggests incomplete activation, likely leaving residual volatiles or inorganic content. In contrast, HAC_{236} balances mass retention and stability, indicating well developed porosity without excessive carbon burn off. The influence of activation parameters is evident: higher $KHCO_3$ concentrations (e.g., HAC_{336}) lead to greater volatile removal but may reduce structural integrity, while longer activation times (e.g., 36 vs. 24 h) enhance stability. The superior thermal resistance of HAC_{236} aligns with its exceptional electrochemical behaviour, confirming that its activation conditions optimize both porosity and stability.

It is important to note that, activation times of 12 h and 48 h were also examined for the 1:1 $KHCO_3$ ratio. However, these conditions did not result in any measurable improvement in capacitance compared to the 24 h and 36 h treatments. This confirms that intermediate durations provide the most effective balance of pore development and electrochemical performance, supporting the conclusion of 36 h as the optimal activation time.

The porous structure of HAC_{236} was analysed using nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K, with the obtained isotherm and pore size distribution curves presented in Fig. 3(b). The adsorption isotherm exhibits a Type I profile with minor Type IV characteristics, confirming that HAC_{236} is predominantly microporous with some mesopore contribution. The steep increase in adsorbed volume at very low relative pressures ($p/p_0 < 0.1$) indicates strong micropore filling, while the gradual rise at higher pressures ($p/p_0 0.1-0.4$) suggests limited mesoporosity. The adsorption and desorption branches show significant overlap, suggesting a highly stable pore. The absence of a sharp plateau at higher pressures further supports the presence of a well developed microporous network with secondary mesopores enhancing molecular transport. The Barrett Joyner Halenda (BJH) pore size distribution Fig. 3 inset further confirms the micropore-dominated nature of HAC_{236} , with dominant peaks at 1–50 nm in, indicating that most of the pore volume originates from small micropores. The BET surface area of HAC_{236} was determined to be 1006 m^2/g , with a total pore volume of 0.586 cm^3/g (adsorption) and 0.588 cm^3/g (desorption), measured at $p/p^* = 0.95$. The BET average pore diameter of 2.33 nm (adsorption) and 2.34 nm (desorption) supports the micropore dominant classification, with mesoporosity playing a minor role. These results confirm that HAC_{236} possesses a hierarchical porous structure, primarily composed of micropores with a small fraction of mesopores.

A comparison of BET surface area values for different samples,

including biochar and activated carbons at varying activation conditions, is presented in Table 1. The BET surface area of HAC_{236} (1006.04 m^2/g) is the highest among all the samples and more than double that of the original biochar (402.38 m^2/g) indicating that the activation conditions used for HAC_{236} resulted in the most developed porous network.

X ray photoelectron spectroscopy reveals clear quantitative differences in surface bonding before and after activation as shown in Fig. 4. Table 2 shows that for the raw biochar, the C1s spectrum is dominated by C-C/C-H bonds at 284.8 eV with an atomic contribution of 50.2 at. %, together with C-O at 23.6 at. %, C-O at 7.0 at. %, O-C=O at 4.3 at. % and CO_3 at 1.1 at. %. After $KHCO_3$ activation, the C-C and C-H contribution decreases to 33.3 at. %, while oxygen-containing bonds increase markedly. The C-O fraction rises to 29.9 at. % and the C=O fraction increases to 14.4 at. %, more than doubling relative to the biochar. The most significant change is observed for the carbonate CO_3 component, which increases from 1.1 at. % to 4.2 at. %, representing an approximately fourfold increase, a small amount of carbonate was already present in biochar as per the report provided by the supplier. This pronounced increase in carbonate species is a clear chemical signature of $KHCO_3$ -based activation. The O1s spectra show a corresponding increase in O-C=O oxygen from 2.2 at% to 2.6 at%, further supporting the formation of carboxyl and carbonate-related surface groups. These quantitative changes indicate that $KHCO_3$ activation leads to pronounced surface oxidation and defect formation, resulting in a clear redistribution of surface bonding from predominantly graphitic carbon toward oxygen-containing functional groups. This evolution in surface chemistry is consistent with the increased defect density observed by Raman spectroscopy Fig. 2(a, b) and supports improved interfacial interactions with the aqueous electrolyte, helping to explain the enhanced electrochemical performance of HAC_{236} .

The rheology of the HAC_{236} ink was evaluated to understand its stability and processing characteristics. All measurements were carried out at room temperature using a rotational rheometer (DHR-2, TA Instruments Inc., USA) equipped with a 20 mm parallel plate geometry. As shown in Fig. S3b, the storage modulus G' exceeds the loss modulus G'' by nearly an order of magnitude throughout the measured frequency range. Such behaviour confirms that HAC_{236} forms a dominantly elastic network at rest, which helps prevent sedimentation and promotes uniform particle distribution within the slurry. Similar elastic responses have been reported for porous carbon inks with hierarchical structures, where surface functionalities and interparticle contacts provide structural integrity. The flow sweep in Fig. S3b shows that the slurry shows strong shear thinning, with viscosity decreasing from about 3800 cP at low shear to below 1 cP at high shear. This allows the slurry to flow easily during coating while rapidly recovering its structure at rest, this observed behaviour lies within the rheological window reported for printable activated carbon inks, indicating that the HAC_{236} formulation is suitable for future coating and printing-based electrode fabrication

Table 1
Quantified specific surface area values for biochar and hydrothermally activated carbons.

Sample Name	Biochar	HAC ₁ 24	HAC ₁ 36	HAC ₂ 24	HAC ₂ 36	HAC ₃ 24	HAC ₃ 36
BET Specific Surface Area (m ² /g)	402 ± 17	463 ± 18	496 ± 19	854 ± 33	1006 ± 30	652 ± 26	630 ± 24

Fig. 4. XPS spectra of (a) survey scan, (b) C1s and (c) O1s for HAC₂36, and XPS spectra of (d) survey scan, (e) C1s and (f) O1s for biochar.

Table 2
XPS bonding configurations and atomic concentrations for Biochar and HAC₂36.

Elements	Components	Biochar (At. %)	HAC ₂ 36 (At. %)
C1s	C-C/C-H	50.18	33.29
	C-O	23.61	29.93
	C=O	7.00	14.42
	O-C=O	4.33	4.73
	(CO ₃) ²⁻	1.05	4.15
O1s	C-O	11.66	10.87
	O-C=O	2.18	2.61

[52,53].

The FESEM images shown in Fig. 5 illustrate the morphological evolution of the material during activation. As observed in Fig. 5(a-c), the raw biochar exhibits relatively compact particles with smoother surfaces and limited surface features. After activation, a clear change in morphology is observed in Fig. 5(d-f), where the material displays increased fragmentation, angular particle formation, and a noticeably rougher surface texture. These features indicate carbon framework etching and structural breakdown during activation. While individual pores are not directly resolved in the FESEM images, the observed morphological changes are consistent with activation-induced modification of the carbon structure. The development of micro- and mesopores is confirmed by BET surface area and pore size distribution analysis, and this structural evolution is in agreement with the improved electrochemical performance observed for the activated samples.

In order to further evaluate the stability of activated carbon after

long-term GCD cycles, FESEM images were taken from the HAC₂36 before and after 10,000 cycles, as shown in Fig. 6. Comparing the images, it can be concluded that the overall porous morphology of the HAC₂36 is largely maintained after extended cycling, which indicates that the material preserves its structural framework throughout the repeated charge-discharge processes. Nevertheless, in the post-cycled sample, some localized enlargement of surface cavities is observed (Fig. 6(d-f)). These newly formed larger pores suggest that some localized degradation or minor structural stress took place, which is consistent with the moderate capacitance retention observed after 10,000 cycles. Overall, the FESEM comparison of HAC₂36 before and after long-term cycling, confirms a good structural integrity while undergoing slight surface modifications throughout the extending operation.

3.2. Electrochemical characterization

The electrochemical behaviour was evaluated using CV, a technique applied to assess intrinsic capacitive characteristics within the potential window of 0–1.2 V. As shown in Fig. 7(a), the cyclic voltammograms offered insight into the electrochemical response of all specimens recorded at a scan rate of 5 mV/s. CV curves were converted to current density vs. voltage from current vs. voltage to eliminate the effect of difference in mass loading of different devices. Overall, all devices showed a quasi-rectangular profile consistent with EDLC behaviour of AC. Best performing sample HAC₂36 showed the highest area under the curve across applied scan rates, as shown in Fig. S1 indicative of its superior energy storage performance. Remarkably, the devices upheld symmetric behaviour even at elevated scan rates, affirming favourable

Fig. 5. FESEM images of raw biochar (a–c) and HAC_{236} (d–f) at three magnification scales.

Fig. 6. FESEM images of activated carbon (HAC_{236}) electrode (a–c) before and (d–f) after 10,000 GCD cycles.

electrochemical stability and commendable rate capability.

Energy storage capacitance was further tested via GCD at various current of 1 mA within the potential range of 0–1.2 V. A quasi-triangular profile was observed in all samples as shown in Fig. 7(b), indicative of

EDLC behaviour. HAC_{236} again showed the best discharge times with respect to the current density applied. Even though absolute best discharge time was shown by HAC_{236} but it was due to the higher mass loading thus a lower current density, as shown in Fig. S2. Optimal

Fig. 7. (a) Comparative cyclic voltammograms from CV characterization of prepared materials at 5 mV/s scan rates, (b) Comparative discharge curves from GCD characterization of prepared materials at 1 mA current.

performance of HAC_{236} was further quantified with Eq. (2) to a specific capacitance of 27.13 F/g at 0.08 A/g or 1 mA current as shown in Fig. 8 (a) in comparison with other devices which showed specific capacitances ranging from 20 to 24 F/g at comparable current densities and same current. These results correlate strongly with the material's textural properties, BET analysis revealed that HAC_{236} achieved the highest surface area (1006 m²/g) and total pore volume (~0.586 cm³/g), with a hierarchical pore structure dominated by micropores (~1–2.5 nm) and supplemented by secondary mesopores. This architecture ensures a large population of accessible ion adsorption sites while also providing diffusion pathways that minimize transport resistance, enabling effective utilization of the surface even at higher current densities. The stability observed in TGA, with controlled degradation and retention of carbon framework, further supports the structural robustness of HAC_{236} and explains its ability to sustain EDLC behaviour under repeated cycling. To comprehensively characterize the device, the specific energy (E) and specific power (P) were calculated using Eqs. (3) and (4), and the resulting values were plotted in a Ragone diagram, as shown in Fig. 8(b). At a specific power of approximately 56 W/kg, the optimized HAC_{236} sample exhibited a specific energy of 5.4 Wh/kg. Even under a high operational load of 676 W/kg, the device retained a notable specific energy of 3.3 Wh/kg. It is worth noting that in all cases, current density (A/g) and specific capacitance (F/g) were calculated with respect to the mass of active material (activated carbon) in a single device, excluding the current collector, separator, and electrolyte.

The remarkable durability and long cycle life of supercapacitor device remain critical advantages, ensuring sustained performance across extended operational lifetimes. Among performance metrics, capacitance retention is widely accepted as a reliable indicator of cyclability and structural resilience. As illustrated in Fig. 9(a), the HAC_{236} device maintained approximately 85 % of its initial capacitance after 10,000 galvanostatic charge-discharge cycles at a current density of 0.8 A/g,

worth noting is the fact that most of loss came in first 2000 cycles after which a relative stability was achieved, highlighting its stability. This robust retention surpasses many previously reported biomass derived carbon materials [54] and confirms the structural integrity imparted by the hydrothermal KHCO₃ activation protocol. Notably, the progressive increase in equivalent series resistance (ESR), recorded at intervals of 2000 cycles and shown in the inset of Fig. 9(a), rose from 16 Ω to 21 Ω over 10,000 cycles. This resistance growth is often attributed to gradual modifications at the electrode-electrolyte interface, including surface oxidation, partial pore blockage, and loss of conductivity pathways due to mechanical or electrochemical stress. These mechanisms are consistent with changes reported for carbon based SCs under long term operation [55–57].

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), conducted over a frequency range of 10 mHz–1 MHz, further substantiated these observations (Fig. 9(b)). The Nyquist plots revealed an increase in the high frequency intercept post cycling, confirming ESR growth, while an enlarged semicircle at mid frequencies signaled elevated charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}). Additionally, the Warburg region became more inclined after cycling, indicating increased ion diffusion resistance due to microstructural degradation, likely from partial collapse or saturation of the pore network. Fitting parameters obtained from the proposed equivalent circuit are displayed in Table 3. These findings correlate with the porosity profile derived from N₂ adsorption-desorption measurements, where HAC_{236} exhibited a high BET surface area of 1006 m²/g and a total pore volume of ~0.586 cm³/g. The adsorption isotherm displayed a Type I shape with minor Type IV features, confirming a micropore-dominant architecture with limited mesoporosity. Pore size distribution revealed dominant micropores in the range of 1–2.5 nm, which, while beneficial for high capacitance, are more susceptible to blockage over repeated cycling. Nonetheless, the hierarchical porous framework of HAC_{236} preserved sufficient ion accessible surface area to

Fig. 8. (a) Specific capacitances of HAC-based devices at varying current densities, (b) Ragone plot of HAC_{236} showing specific energy and specific power.

Fig. 9. (a) Capacitance retention of HAC_{236} over 10,000 cycles (the inset shows the evolution of ESR during cycling), (b) Nyquist plots showing data from before and after cycling, the solid lines are the fitting results (insets showing the modified Randles circuit used for fitting and impedance spectra at high frequencies)).

Table 3

Equivalent circuit parameters for HAC_{236} based SC before and after cycling.

Device	Element					
	R_0 (Ω)	W_0 (DW)	R_1 (Ω)	CPE ₀		C_0 (mF)
				Y_0 ($\mu S s^\alpha$)	α (m)	
Before Cycling	17.2	18.9	2.05	117	667	338
After Cycling	21.8	14.6	12.9	0.287	730	246

sustain EDLC behavior with minimal structural compromise, as further evidenced by the capacitive slope at low frequencies remaining near vertical, an indication of ideal EDLC response. Overall, the combined electrochemical and structural analyses confirm the robustness of material and validate the use of $KHCO_3$ assisted hydrothermal activation as an effective route for producing robust, sustainable activated carbons suitable for long life energy storage applications.

The specific capacitance of our best AC, around 27 F/g, is consistent with other bare activated carbons tested in neutral aqueous electrolytes, as summarized in Table 4. Although higher values above 100 F/g have been reported, those typically involve aggressive KOH activation, the addition of pseudocapacitive agents such as MnO_2 or polyaniline, or the use of electrolytes that are not biodegradable. Recent studies on battery type electrodes show that hybrid supercapacitors (SCs) can reach very high capacity and long cycle life [58,59], but at the cost of complex metal oxide synthesis and less sustainable electrolytes. Here we instead focus on a biochar derived EDLC carbon made by a green route, accepting moderate capacitance in exchange for benign chemistry, simple processing and better end of life compatibility. Our results show

Table 4

A comparison of our optimized AC with ACs activated by various methods.

Materials	Activation Method	Specific Energy (Wh/kg)	Specific Power (W/kg)	Capacitance Retention (%) (Cycles)	Specific Capacitance (F/g) at Current Density (A/g)	Electrolyte with Potential Window (V)	References
Waste graphite from spent dry-cell batteries	800 °C for 2 h with KOH	40.20	1440	60 (200)	20 at 0.5	1M NaOH with 2	[54]
Carbonized wood from a mixture of deciduous trees obtained via pyrolysis at 500–700 °C for 10 min in air atmosphere.	Hydrodynamic cavitation in a 50 L vessel (2.5 kW) for 3 h at 70 °C using a 1:3 HNO_3 : H_2SO_4 acid mixture.	0.53	51	100 (10000)	24 at 0.25	1M H_2SO_4 with 0.8	[60]
Rice husk-derived activated carbon (RHAC) containing 50 wt% carbon and 50 wt% silica.	CO_2 activation at 875 °C for 1 h following N_2 preheating	–	–	95 (5000)	19 at 0.05	1M tetraethylammonium tetrafluoroborate in propylene carbonate with 2.5	[61]
HAC_{236}	Green hydrothermal activation	5.4	56	85 (10000)	27 at 0.08	2.85M NaCl with 1.2	This work

that even under mild and environmentally safe activation conditions, using a NaCl electrolyte and a chitosan binder, it is possible to achieve capacitance and long-term stability that are competitive with systems developed through less sustainable routes. For example KOH-activated graphite, achieves high energy and power densities (40.20 Wh/kg and 1440 W/kg), it does so at the expense of environmental safety and scalability, relying on corrosive alkalis and non-biodegradable 1 M NaOH electrolytes [54]. Likewise, carbon from deciduous wood subjected to HNO_3 - H_2SO_4 cavitation treatment shows full cycle retention but depends on aggressive acid mixtures [60]. In contrast, HAC_{236} , synthesized under biocompatible conditions and tested in a biodegradable 2.85 M NaCl electrolyte, delivers a specific energy of 5.4 Wh/kg and a specific power of 56 W/kg. It maintains 85 % capacitance retention over 10,000 cycles and achieves a specific capacitance of 27 F/g at 1.2 V values that compare favourably with, or exceed, those of several materials activated using CO_2 or KOH, including Rice husk-derived activated carbon (RHAC), which requires higher temperatures and uses synthetic organic electrolytes [61]. Notably, our approach involves no toxic binders or additives and maintains excellent rate capability, demonstrating that environmentally conscious design can deliver practical and scalable solutions without sacrificing performance. HAC_{236} thus represents a compelling case for sustainable electrode development in next generation SCs.

4. Conclusion

In this work, a sustainable, hydrothermal activation approach employing $KHCO_3$ was successfully applied to convert biomass derived biochar into high performance activated carbon suitable for

supercapacitor applications. The activation method, performed under moderate conditions (200 °C for 36 h), demonstrated a remarkable mass yield of ~90 %, substantially higher than conventional techniques. This approach notably improved the porous structure, elevating the BET specific surface area from an initial 420 m²/g to approximately 1006 m²/g, primarily consisting of micropores complemented by a minor mesoporous fraction. Electrochemical assessments validated the superior capacitive performance of *HAC₂₃₆*, achieving a specific capacitance of 27.13 F/g at 0.08 A/g and impressive specific energy (5.4 Wh/kg at 56 W/kg) that remains substantial even under high power conditions. Additionally, the device demonstrated excellent cycling stability, retaining 85 % of its initial capacitance after extensive cycling. The developed method addresses significant limitations of conventional chemical activation, particularly eliminating the environmental and safety risks associated with the use of corrosive chemicals such as KOH and reducing energy requirements. Given its high yield, low activation temperature, and compatibility with sustainable biomass resources, this hydrothermal KHCO₃ assisted method offers a promising alternative for large scale production of activated carbon devices. Future efforts should be directed towards optimizing reaction parameters along with exploration of other green activating agents and exploring diverse biomass sources to enhance electrochemical performance further, advancing towards fully sustainable, commercially viable energy storage solutions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kanwar Muhammad Adam: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Chirag Mevada:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Vijay Singh Parihar:** Methodology, Data curation. **Amit Tewari:** Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Hamed Pourkheirollah:** Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Jari Keskinen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration. **Matti Mäntysalo:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no financial or personal relationships that could influence the work presented in this article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2025.108857>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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